

Vaccine hesitancy has become a high priority of the World Health Organization. Vaccine refusal or delayed vaccination are considered vaccine hesitant behaviors. To better understand people who are hesitant but still choose to be vaccinated (hesitant adopters), this study explored trusted sources of COVID-19 information in the US. Identifying trusted sources of information can inform future public health messaging campaigns aimed at increasing vaccine adoption.

WHERE:

COVID-19 vaccine events in churches, health clinics, and communities across the state of Arkansas

WHEN?

April 2021 – July 2021

WHO?

The study included 867 diverse adults between 18 and 44 years old who received the COVID-19 vaccine, but indicated they were hesitant to do so. The sample was racially and ethnically diverse; however, women and people who identified as college educated were overrepresented.

ANALYSIS SOURCES

- Population and economic information were based on the **2014-2018 American Community Survey**.
- Vaccination sites were pulled from the NYC Vaccine Finder website.
- Testing and vaccination data were pulled from the NYC Health COVID-19: Data website.

MEASURES & OBSERVATIONS

- Participants completed a 10-minute survey during the required post-vaccine observation time.
- The survey captured socioeconomic demographics like age, sex, race/ethnicity, education level, marital status, and employment status. Additional questions focused on hesitancy and trusted sources of information.
- A codebook was developed as part of the qualitative descriptive process to assess responses to open-ended questions.

KEY FINDINGS

- Evaluation of the qualitative data found that 92.5% of the coded responses fell into one of four themes. These themes represent trusted sources of information identified by hesitant adopters.
 - **Health care/Medical science (50.2%)**
 - **Personal relationships (21.8%)**
 - **News and Social Media (16.4%)**
 - **Individual/Myself (4.2%)**
- While the majority of respondents trusted at least one information source, almost **one in ten (7.5%)** did not trust any source of information.

CONCLUSIONS

Some studies suggest trust in healthcare providers and medical scientists has declined, but this and other studies have found that they continue to be the greatest sources of trusted COVID-19 information, including among hesitant adopters.

Family, friends, religious institutions and leaders, and vaccinated individuals are also trusted sources of information for hesitant adopters.

Perception of trustworthiness increases when there is an overlap of expertise and personal social connection (e.g., healthcare provider who is a friend or family member). Nevertheless, lack of trust in traditional sources of information like the news/media and the government was consistent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, healthcare providers, personal relationships, and testimonials from vaccinated individuals should be considered as trusted sources of information when developing COVID-19 campaigns and resources targeting hesitant adopters.

This summary was performed in May 2022. This summary includes only the results of a single study. Other studies may find different results. The study was supported in part by the NIH RADx[®] Underserved Populations (RADx-UP) initiative (NIH 3 R01MD013852-02S3)

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